

Egg predators of rice leaffolder (LF) and their susceptibility to insecticides

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In transplanted fields in Nueva Ecija, Philippines, a mixed population of LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* and *Marasmia patnalis* exceeded 1 moth/linear m. In insecticide-free plots, however, leaf damage did not exceed 15%, leading us to suspect that egg predators were suppressing LF. We screened five possible predators in mylar cylinder cages kept outdoors.

Field-collected LF adults oviposited overnight on potted reproductive-stage rice plants. Leaves with about 50 eggs per plant were marked. Plants were placed in cages for 24 h with 5 of each suspected predator species. The predators significantly reduced the number of oviposited eggs (Table 1). Five adult *Micraspis crocea* and *Synharmonia octomaculata*, and nymphs and adults of *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* caused 21-32% egg mortality. Egg numbers were reduced 85% by five *Metioche vittaticollis* and 13% by *Anaxipha longipennis*.

Farmers normally spray insecticide 2-4 times beginning 3-5 wk after transplanting. Many fields subsequently have 40-80% LF damage, a possible sign

Table 1. Evaluation of LF egg predators, ^a Nueva Ecija, Philippines, Oct-Nov 1984.

Species	Egg mortality ^b (%)
Gryllidae (adults)	
<i>Metioche vittaticollis</i> (Stal)	85 a
<i>Anaxipha longipennis</i> (Serville)	73 a
Coccinellidae (adults)	
<i>Micraspis crocea</i> (Mulsant) and <i>Synharmonia octomaculata</i> (Fabricius)	32 b
Miridae	
<i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i> Reuter adults	28 b
nymphs	21 b
Untreated	0 c

^aAv of 10 replications. Each replication received 5 field-collected predators from insecticide-free plots, ^bMortality 24 h after predator release. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P < 0.05) by DMRT.

Table 2. Contact toxicity of commercial insecticides against 2 species of gryllid predators. ^a Nueva Ecija, Philippines, Oct-Nov 1984.

Insecticide ^b	Mortality ^c (%)	
	<i>Metioche</i> sp. 48 HAT	<i>Anaxipha</i> sp. 48 HAT
Monocrotophos 30 EC	95 a	95 a
MIPC 50 WP	95 a	100 a
Chlorpyrifos 20% + BPMC + 11% EC	100 a	100 a
Methyl parathion 50 EC	100 a	100 a
Azinphos-ethyl 40 EC	20 c	44 c
BPMC 50 EC	83 ab	100 a
Cypermethrin 5 EC	68 b	97 a
Methomyl 20 EC	100 a	100 a
Endosulfan 35 EC	34 c	80 b

^aAv of 6 replications. HAT = hours after treatment. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by DRMT. ^bApplied as foliar spray at 0.4 kg ai/ha. ^cMortality adjusted by Abbott's formula.

of insecticide-induced resurgence. To confirm this, we studied the mortality of the two cricket predators after applying commonly used insecticides.

Forty-five days after transplanting, potted rice plants were sprayed with insecticides at 0.4 kg ai/ha. When the

spray dried, 10 adult crickets collected from insecticide-free plots were caged on the plants. Mortality was measured after 48 h. Both species were highly susceptible, but *Metioche* less so, to all insecticides except azinphos-ethyl and endosulfan (Table 2). ☞

Efficacy of four insecticides against major rice pests in Tamil Nadu, India

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In Sep 1984 and Feb 1985 we assessed the efficacy of four insecticides (see table) against yellow stem borer (YSB), leaffolder (LF), and whorl maggot (RWM). Insecticides were applied to

CR 1009 3 times at 20-d intervals beginning 10 d after transplanting (DT). Insect populations were recorded at 10-d intervals beginning 20 DT. Percent YSB incidence was determined by counting total tillers and those with deadhearts and whiteheads. LF and RWM incidence was calculated based on total leaves and infested leaves.

All insecticide treatments significantly and similarly reduced pest incidence and gave higher yield than the untreated control (see table). ☞

Cartap and 3 other insecticides for controlling YSB, LF, and RWM, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Mean percent incidence ^a			Yield (t/ha)
		YSB	LF	RWM	
<i>Granules</i>					
Cartap 50 SP	1.0	14 a	9 a	14 a	1.3
Cartap 50 SP	1.5	14 a	9 a	14 a	1.5
Carbofuran 3 G	0.75	14 a	9 a	14 a	1.5
Chlorpyrifos 10 G	1.0	14 a	9 a	14 a	1.7
Untreated check	—	21 b	13 b	18 b	1.0
<i>Spray</i>					
Cartap 50 SP	1.0	17 a	11 a	11 a	1.3
Cartap 50 SP	1.5	17 a	10 a	11 a	1.2
Phosphamidon 85 EC	0.5	17 a	11 a	13 a	1.0
Chlorpyrifos 20 EC	0.5	17 a	11 a	12 a	1.6
Untreated check	—	25 b	14 b	17 b	0.8

^aArcsine transformed values for the mean percent incidence of 5 replications. Separation of means by DMRT at the 5% level.